

Factors affecting T1 accuracy and quantification of fibrosis

R.M.U.K.G.M.S. Bandara¹ and J.P. Wansapura²

¹*Department of Nuclear Science, University of Colombo*

²*Department of Physics, University of Colombo*

The study was based on simulated magnetic resonance images (MRI) created by MATLAB software. The aim of the study was to estimate the effects of signal to noise ratio (SNR) and flip-angle variations, in the determination of longitudinal relaxation time T1. Simulated MRI experiments were used to determine the optimal image pixel sampling method to be used in the calculation of T1. Five sampling methods were used to determine mean values of MR image: (1) Dividing the image into four equal blocks, (2) Dividing the image in the direction of flip angle variation, (3) Dividing the image in the direction perpendicular to the flip angle variation, (4) Taking mean pixel value of whole image, and (5) considering the values pixels by pixel. Calculation of T1 using the whole image was identified as the most effective approach, with a minimum deviation of 2.3 ms from the reference value 1000 ms. Minimum and maximum error percentages for flip-angle range 160⁰ to 180⁰ and SNR = 20 were 0.283% (whole image) and 3.288% (in the direction of flip angle variation) respectively. As expected, results show that the minimum deviations occur in narrowed flip angle regions towards 180 degrees and with high SNR values. T1 based extracellular volume (ECV) fraction error was found to be 21.78% for the whole image averaging method and 36.39% for four equal slice method at the lowest SNR (2.5) value.

Keywords: MRI, T1 calculation, fibrosis